

Importance of Yoga for women's health in modern life

Dr. Pranita Baishya

Asst. Prof, Pub Bongsor College

"Yoga is the journey of the self through the self, to the self"

-The Bhagabat Gita

Abstract:

There is nothing more important than self care of our body. Women are constantly pressurized between the role and responsibilities of work place and home. Women are multitasked playing multiple roles like daughter, sister, wife, mother, friend, colleague for which they often deprioritise themselves and neglect their own health. They try to maintain a balance between home and career. This negligence to their own health is the root cause of many diseases that women face. Since women are backbone of the family as well as the society, it is essential to keep them strong mentally and physically. This paper tries to study the importance of women's health in today's life and how Yoga can help them reach their fitness.

Keywords: Yoga, Women's health, Asanas, modern life

Introduction:

Yoga is one of the most ancient arts that connect the mind and body. It investigates the nature of soul through its discipline which unites the mortal being with the immortal supreme spirit. Today Yoga is an integral part of life. It is an exercise that we perform by balancing the elements of our body. In addition to this yoga helps us meditating and relax. It also helps us to keep control of our bodies as well as mind. It is a great way for relaxing our stress and anxiety. Various styles of yoga combine various physical postures and stretches, breathing techniques and meditation to improve physical fitness, reduce stress and attain mental balance.

The word 'Yoga' or 'Yog' is derived from the Sanskrit root 'Yuj' that means "Union or to join or to unite or to connect." It is the union of our body, mind and spirit. It is a practice that helps one connect with the inner mind and consciousness. Today yoga is practiced all over the world, bringing physical and mental fitness to millions of men and women.

Origin of Yoga:

Yoga's origin can be traced to northern India over 5000 years ago. The practice of yoga is believed to start with the very dawn of civilization. In the yogic lore, Shiva is seen as the first yogi or Adiyogi. The word Yoga was first mentioned in ancient sacred text the Rig Veda. It was India that the yogic system found its fullest expression. Though yoga was being practiced in the Pre Vedic period, the great sage Maharshi Patanjali systematized and codified the then existing practice of yoga, its meaning and its related knowledge through his yoga sutras. Maharshi Patanjali, the founder of yoga was the first yogi to truly understand and explain the meaning of yoga and the true purpose behind it.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the relevance of yoga in modern life
2. To study the benefits of Yoga in women's life
3. To study some of the Asanas helpful for women's health.

Methodology of the study:

The research methodology of this article is based on secondary data. All the data has been collected from books, journals, magazines, published articles on this area. To gather more information, the help of the website is also considered.

Relevance of yoga in modern life:

Yoga is a science of living. It needs to be incorporated in daily life. It works on physical, mental, emotional, social and spiritual levels of human beings. Yoga helps in improving the quality of life.

In the hustle and bustle of modern life, our emotional stability declines. According to the National Institutes of Health, scientific evidence shows that yoga supports stress management, mental health, mindfulness, healthy eating, weight loss and quality sleep. In the present scenario of the world life is so chaotic and stressful that even thinking of early days soothes our heart and brain. The existence of people with the passage of time has changed. Science has dominated the present and we all fully depend on it. Physical labour has reduced and ultimately the health of this generation has weakened due to lack of labour and exercise. Too much consumption of fast food especially by the young generation has also been detrimental to health. During these modern days of competition, life is so hard and stressful that human being is unable to cope up and hence suffering from various life style disease and disorder. Yoga provides the best solution of physical and mental problems to which the modern man is suffering. Man cannot deal with these problems except yoga. If it is much of practiced regularly, all types of physical and mental problems will be solved.

Today, millions of people across the world are following yoga either in the form of one particular asana or a combination of many. Modern yogis claims that yogic exercises cure various diseases like obesity, diabetics, dislocation of disc, respiratory problems, arthritis of various types and various spine problems, high blood pressure besides stress and even cholesterol problems and heart diseases. Yoga guru Swami Ramdev and many of his cults are making yoga more popular all over the world by demonstrating modern physical exercise of yoga.

Benefits of Yoga:

Yoga is not a religion. It is a way of living that aims towards a healthy mind in a healthy body. Man is a physical, mental and spiritual being. Yoga helps in developing the balance between all these three. Yoga as a practice has innumerable benefits that positively affect an individual both physically and mentally. Some of the benefits of Yoga are as follows:-

- Yoga improves strength, balance and flexibility

- Improves brain function
- Lower stress level
- Lowers blood pressure
- Increases blood circulation
- Improves lung capacity
- Relieves anxiety
- Lowers blood sugar in diabetes
- Yoga lowers the risk of heart disease
- Yoga helps with back pain relieve
- Yoga develops the immune system
- Yoga improves respiration, energy and vitality.

Apart from the above common benefits there are few additional benefits that yoga offers which are specific to women. These are:-

1. **Yoga can support hormonal balance.** Many women undergo hormonal fluctuations throughout their life. From puberty to menopause most of the female experience enormous hormonal changes. Regular yoga practice can help them balancing these hormones. Yoga can reduce symptoms like mood swings, bloating, hot flashes, sleeplessness, skin problem etc.
2. **Yoga can relieve menstrual pain.** Every month many women feel panic about the painful cramps their period brings. This type of problems can be relieved by doing some yoga poses.
3. **Yoga may enhance fertility.** For some women being pregnant is not an easy task and become stressful. Yoga has been shown to improve both male and female fertility. By incorporating some Asanas regularly in our daily routine yoga can help to make the body ready to conceive.
4. **Yoga improves flexibility and strength.** With consistent practice yoga enhances flexibility, balance and physical strength. Even the stiff muscle with little flexibility can be improved through yoga over time.

5. **Yoga improves general physical health.** Yoga can also boost our blood circulation and thus reducing the risk of heart disease.
6. **Yoga benefits mental health and wellbeing.** It can reduce anxiety and depression. Focusing on the breath while stretching and moving the body is a great way to pull our mind away from worries and stress.
7. **Yoga can support wellbeing in pregnancy.** The pregnancy symptoms like nausea or shortness of breath can be relieved with the help of yoga. Yoga has been shown to be helpful in building the strength and flexibility of the muscles needed during the labor.
8. **Yoga can boost postpartum recovery.** After giving birth, the body and mind of a woman undergoes tremendous changes. Yoga can play a vital role in postpartum recovery strengthening the core muscles and reducing the emotional stress.

Some Asanas for women's health:

With busy schedule and unhealthy eating habits we have invited a lot of disease and life style issues. Today every fourth women is facing polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS). According to Centre for Biotechnology about 23% of urban Indian female population is obese. Therefore it is necessary for every woman to follow some yogasana. Some Asanas helpful for women are:

1. Pachimottanasana (seated forward bend): This posture is beneficial for losing tummy fat, stretching soulder and back muscles. It also calms nervous system, treat high blood pressure, infertility and tones internal organs.
2. Veerabhadrasana (warrior pose): This asana helps in maintaining balance and strengthens back muscles, hamstring and shoulder muscles and joints.
3. Marjjarasana (Cat/cow pose): This simple asana has multiple benefits. It brings flexibility to the spine, massages internal organs thereby improving digestion and metabolism, relaxes the mind and strengthens wrists and shoulders.
4. Shishuasana (Child pose): This asana is called child pose as it relates to a relaxing posture of a child in its mother's arms. Child pose gently massages and

tones internal organs and muscles along with providing a good stretch to the body. It helps eliminate back and neck pain and relaxes muscles; rejuvenating the whole body.

5. Ardha Chakrasana (Standing backward bend): This backward bending pose stretches the entire body which helps tone the arm and shoulder muscles and provides a great stretch to the spine. It is considered as one of the best exercises to reduce lower back pain and cure respiratory disorders.
6. Hastapadasana (Standing Forward bend): It stretches almost all the muscles in the body, improves the flexibility of the spine and also increases blood circulation.
7. Utkatasana (Chair pose): This pose tones the ankle, thighs, leg and knee. It is a great exercise for the spine, hips and chest muscles. It is an asana that enhances balance in the body.
8. Baddha Konasana (Butterfly pose): This asana got its name from the movement of legs like a butterfly. This asana provides a great stretch to the inner thighs, groin and knees, helps intestines and bowel movement. Pregnant ladies and those who are planning to start a family benefit most from this asana as it improves fertility and facilitates smooth pregnancy.
9. Yoga Nidra (Yogic sleep): This is the ultimate relaxing pose, which is generally practiced towards the end of the yoga session. It involves laying down straight on the mat, eyes closed and trying to relax the whole body. This pose helps the nervous system absorb all the effects of yoga postures practiced.

Conclusion:

The importance of yoga in modern life can be categorized under physical, mental, spiritual benefits. While practicing yoga several people related yoga with physical exercise only. But yoga goes beyond the physical fitness or posture. It includes physical, mental, emotional and spiritual parts of life. Yoga is the right path of living to cope up in the present day situation. Yoga helps in reducing stress, maintaining and improving our physical and mental health.

Today the significance of yoga is flourished in the whole country of the world. Yogic practices are more important in modern life. Yoga makes human being stronger and fighter in our challenges of life. It is a simple exercise with great benefits that do not require heavy machinery and equipments. It only requires motivation to practice regularly. If practiced regularly Yoga can transform an individual physically, mentally and spiritually. It is beneficial for the common women who want to bring changes in her body and transform her life with Yoga. Realizing the importance of Yoga, 21st June of every year is celebrated as International Yoga Day. This event is celebrated to create the awareness of the wholesome effects of yoga among the public all over the world.

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